

ALGORITHM FOR DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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Relevance. Regardless of the duration of pain and gestational age, a clinically confirmed diagnosis of acute appendicitis requires immediate surgical intervention. In the study groups, diagnostic errors in the pre-hospital stage, especially associated with prolonged gestation, were high. In the retrospective subgroup of the study, this diagnosis was confirmed in 34% of 45 pregnant women with suspected acute appendicitis within the first 4-8 hours, and in 44.4% of 90 pregnant women in the prospective group, which clearly demonstrates the difficulties in diagnosing acute appendicitis in pregnant women. Diagnostic errors in the II and III trimesters of pregnancy were observed in 16.7%. Incorrect diagnoses at referral: threat of premature termination of pregnancy, acute pyelonephritis, renal colic, gastritis, duodenal ulcer, "acute abdomen". Errors in diagnosis can lead to inappropriate hospitalization, delayed treatment, and other complications.

Aim. To improve the results of surgical treatment of acute appendicitis in pregnant women.

Algorithm. This algorithm was used in all 90 patients of the main group.

In the first stage, the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in pregnant women in all study groups was based on the assessment of painful and paraclinical symptoms, as well as laboratory parameters.

As a second diagnostic stage, an abdominal ultrasound examination was performed in all pregnant women in the main group.

Diagnostic laparoscopy was the 3rd stage of the algorithm, which was performed in pregnant women in the I and II trimesters, who did not confirm or exclude the diagnosis of acute appendicitis within 2-4 hours.

When comparing the two groups, in the main group (where the proposed diagnostic and treatment algorithm was used), an accurate diagnosis was established in 11.4% of patients within the first 3 hours, and in the comparison group (where the proposed diagnostic and treatment algorithm was not used), this was 8% of patients. In the first 3-6 hours, the diagnosis of acute appendicitis was established in 24.3% of the main group and 16% of the comparison group. In the main group, most patients spent 6-12 hours to verify the diagnosis, while in the comparison group - up to a day (40% in both groups). When using the

proposed diagnostic and treatment algorithm, an accurate diagnosis was made in 76.7% of patients within the first 12 hours, while in other cases this result was achieved in 48% of patients. It is known that the diagnosis of acute appendicitis in different trimesters of pregnancy is quite difficult, and errors and delays in diagnosis can lead to various obstetric and surgical complications. In order to solve this problem, by using the staged diagnosis and treatment algorithm developed and proposed by us, it was possible to reduce the period of diagnosis of acute appendicitis in pregnant women by 1.6 times.

